

Guide how to use the Digital Twin as a mechanism to obtain requirements from digital building permit

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Authors
1.0	02/05/2024	Frist draft	Mayte Toscano (OGC)

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How to use this guide

In this chapter, you will find detailed instructions on how to navigate the Guide and get the most out of it. This guide is designed to serve as a comprehensive resource for both **beginners and advanced experts** seeking a practical approach to learning how to extract requirements from digital twins to ensure compliance with building and zoning regulations. It also aims to guide users on how to exploit the potential offered by digital twins in urban planning.

Reading through this guide

This guide provides extensive information on theoretical and practical aspects of obtaining standard city models using 3D information, and how this information can help to obtain planning data.

The main audience for this guide is **architects and data analysts** who will be working with 3D models.

However, **urban project managers and managers** can also benefit from this guide.

This Guide is as result of the **ACCORD project** is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative by the European Union. Its main goal is **to automate building permit and compliance processes using Building Information Modeling (BIM) and**

other data sources. ACCORD is developing a Semantic Framework, which will be showcased in five real-life construction projects across Europe, specifically in Finland, Estonia, Germany, the UK, and Spain.

This framework includes **semantic interoperability, a rule formalization tool, and integrated microservices for building permit verification and compliance**. The focus is on improving efficiency and reducing errors in permit processes through a semi-automated workflow that incorporates many manual steps of the building permit process.

Language

This guide is written in **technical language** and assumes familiarity with BIM, digital twins, and urban planning.

However, to reach the largest possible audience, an attempt has been made to define and cover all the concepts used. The Glossary used in this document is:

Term	Definition
BIM	Building Information Modeling
GIS	Geographical Information System
GML	Geographic Markup Language
LoD	Level of Detail
LOI	Level of Information
ISO	International Standards Organisation

What you won't find in this guide

In this guide, we have intentionally excluded some important elements in this guide to focus on practical and non-prescriptive content. **We haven't provided any specific project** specifications because every project is unique and has its own requirements and parameters. This material aims to equip you with theoretical and methodological tools to approach your project with a flexible and open mind.

Furthermore, **we haven't included a list of validations for Digital Twin**. Although validations are crucial, they are highly variable and dependent on the context, so it's more practical to address them in a customized manner for each project.

Lastly, any **guide on format transformations is omitted**. This document isn't meant to be a technical manual on data manipulation, but rather a compilation that helps you understand the underlying structures and processes that enable the effective digitization of a physical asset into its digital counterpart.

In summary, this guide is **designed to inspire and provide a strong conceptual and practical foundation**, leaving the necessary space for each professional or technical team to apply, adapt, and extend these insights to the specificities of their project.

New paradigm for building and managing cities

At the crossroads of the 21st century, cities face monumental challenges. The explosive growth of the population, accelerated urbanization, and pressure on natural resources are creating an unprecedented demand to find innovative solutions that allow for building and managing more efficient, sustainable, and livable urban environments.

To these issues, the **impact of climate change on cities is added**. As the world faces changes in climate patterns, cities must adapt and transform to ensure sustainability and long-term resilience.

One of the most direct manifestations of climate change in cities is the increase in temperatures. The urban heat **island effect, exacerbated by the concentration of buildings and asphalt** that absorb and retain heat, is further intensified by the global temperature rise. This not only affects the quality of life by increasing cooling costs and energy demand but can also cause serious public health problems such as heat strokes and the exacerbation of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases.

The **change in precipitation** patterns is another critical effect of climate change affecting cities. Events of intense rainfall and more frequent and severe storms can lead to **urban flooding**, especially in areas with insufficient or outdated drainage infrastructure. This not only causes significant structural damage but also disrupts daily life, affects the local economy, and increases risks to public health due to the spread of water-borne diseases.

In the face of these challenges, **urban planning and design must evolve**. Cities are adopting strategies for **sustainable urbanism** that include the creation of green infrastructure, such as parks and green roofs, which can help mitigate the heat island effect and improve water absorption during heavy rains. Additionally, the integration of efficient public transport systems and the promotion of non-motorized mobility are essential to reduce carbon emissions.

The challenges described also influence **building regulations and construction codes**. New buildings must meet higher standards of energy efficiency and resistance to extreme weather conditions and environmental impact. This involves the use of sustainable materials and construction techniques that not only reduce greenhouse gas emissions but also offer safety and durability against extreme climate events.

In conclusion, the impact of climate change on cities requires a profound and **adaptive review of urbanism**. Cities that anticipate and adapt to these conditions will not only improve the quality of life for their residents but will also set a model for urban resilience and environmental sustainability.

In this context, two disruptive concepts are emerging as fundamental pillars for the transformation of our cities: **Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Digital Twins**.

Building Information Modeling (BIM)

Toward a Revolution in Construction and Urban Planning

Building Information Modeling (BIM) has emerged as a revolutionary technology that is radically transforming the way construction projects are planned, designed, built, and managed. Unlike traditional methods of design and construction, which rely on 2D drawings and two-dimensional documents, **BIM utilizes three-dimensional digital models that contain detailed information about each component of a structure or urban project.**

The adoption of BIM in the urban context has proven to be especially beneficial in multiple aspects. For example, in the design and planning process, BIM enables closer collaboration among architects, engineers, contractors, and other professionals involved in a project. By working in a shared digital environment, **teams can better coordinate their efforts, identify potential conflicts, and make real-time adjustments, leading to more informed decision-making and optimization of urban designs.**

Furthermore, during the construction phase, BIM offers greater **accuracy and efficiency** by allowing visualization and simulation of the entire construction process before work begins. This helps to reduce errors, minimize rework, and optimize the construction sequence, resulting in significant time and cost savings for developers and contractors.

Real Example: Urban Renewal Project in Barcelona

An example of the impact of BIM on urban construction and management can be found in the urban renewal project of Plaza de las Glòries Catalanes in Barcelona, Spain. This project aimed to transform one of the city's most emblematic urban areas into a more accessible, green, and sustainable public space.

By employing BIM methodologies from the initial stages of the project, the design and planning teams were able to create detailed digital models representing not only the geometry of existing buildings and infrastructure but also the complex interactions between different urban elements, such as traffic, public transportation, and pedestrian zones.

These BIM models not only facilitated visualization and communication of the proposed design to all stakeholders but also allowed for the simulation of different scenarios and the evaluation of their impact on mobility, air quality, and pedestrian accessibility. As a result, more informed decisions were made contributing to the overall success of the urban renewal initiative.

In economic terms and within the construction field, the use of BIM results in significant savings both in the execution phase and in the operational phase. During execution, savings come from better planning and coordination of work, reducing errors and conflicts in design, and avoiding task duplication. It is estimated that **economic savings in this phase can range from 10% to 30% of the total project budget.** In the operational phase, BIM helps manage the building's energy and resources efficiently.

Opportunities to save energy and optimize facility performance can be found through understanding the virtual model and monitoring systems and equipment. It is expected that BIM could reduce energy consumption by up to 30% and greenhouse gas emissions by up to 20% during the building's lifespan.

CATEGORY	ASSETS		SECTORS	
	Execution Phase	Exploitation Phase	Construction	Digital
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Save 10% in the execution time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce maintenance costs Reduce operational costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the competitiveness of the sector Increase export capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growth of the digital services industry Single digital market
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce waste volume at construction sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimize operational energy use Evaluate over the entire life cycle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient use of resources Circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient use of data infrastructure resources
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher safety and health Improve discussions and participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better social outcomes (care for patients, students learning...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attract the next generation to the sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data security Attract digital talent to construction

Tabla 1.- EUBIM TaskGroup. 2018

In environmental terms, BIM contributes to sustainability and resource savings in both project phases. During execution, it allows for the optimization of construction processes, reducing waste and minimizing material and energy consumption. This translates into a significant decrease in the project's environmental footprint, with estimated savings in natural resource consumption and a reduction in CO2 emissions.

Regarding the **social aspect**, the application of BIM also brings significant benefits. It improves the **quality of life for building occupants** during the operational phase by enabling efficient management of spaces and services. BIM models offer the option to plan activities and services, enhancing user experience and ensuring more comfortable environments. Additionally, in the execution phase, it enhances workplace safety by allowing for the identification and mitigation of risks before physical construction, thereby reducing accidents and ensuring safer working conditions for staff.

Figure 1.-Scenario 1: Healthy, secure, inclusive urban space

The adoption of BIM not only translates into **efficiency and profitability** but also promotes more **sustainable construction** practices and contributes to social well-being. These combined aspects consolidate BIM as an indispensable tool for addressing contemporary challenges and advancing towards smarter, more efficient, and livable cities.

So, Building Information Modelling methodology has significantly **transformed the construction industry by providing an integrated and collaborative approach to managing projects throughout their entire life cycle**. BIM is implemented in a variety of areas including design, architecture, construction, and maintenance, proving its effectiveness in these fields. In addition, new application areas are being explored such as Smart Cities, environmental management and project certification, among others. Each of these fields can benefit from improvements through the application of BIM methodology, which allows specific requirements to be addressed effectively, thus generating significant benefits.

Digital Twins

Replication of Cities for Smart Management

If BIM represents a revolution in the way cities are designed and built, **Digital Twins** promise to take that revolution a step further by offering virtual replicas of entire cities, powered by **real-time data and advanced simulation capabilities**.

A Digital Twin of a city is an accurate digital representation of its physical infrastructure and operational systems, integrated with real-time data from a wide range of sources, such as IoT sensors, geographic information systems (GIS), public transport records, urban databases and more.

A digital twin can be thought of as a **6-dimensional geospatial model with 3 spatial axes, one phenomenon time axis, one valid time axis, and one “what-if” axis**.

Typically, urban digital twins represent a specific area, such as part of a city, and aspects of that area, such as its built environment, traffic flows, and air circulation. Urban digital twins usually include one or more workflows used to set and update the models they contain and sometimes include data flowing from sensors or active surveys.

An examen: Singapore

One example of the successful implementation of a Digital Twin is in Singapore.

The Singapore government has developed a Digital Twin of the city known as Virtual Singapore, which serves as a comprehensive platform for urban planning, crisis management and data-driven decision-making.

Virtual Singapore combines detailed models of the city's topography, urban infrastructure and buildings with real-time data on traffic, air quality, weather and other relevant factors. To allows urban planners to simulate different scenarios, to managing special events or urban crises, and assess their impact on the urban environment in real time.

The Synergy Between BIM and Digital Twins

Building Smart and Resilient Cities

While BIM and Digital Twins offer impressive capabilities on their own, it is in their integration where their transformative potential truly lies. By **combining BIM's detailed information and simulation capabilities with the real-time data richness and predictive abilities of Digital Twins**, a complete digital environment is created that accurately reflects the physical and operational reality of a city.

This synergy between BIM and Digital Twins enables urban planners and decision-makers to address urban challenges in a **more holistic and proactive manner**. For instance, when planning a new urban development, teams can use BIM models to design and optimize building-level infrastructure, while Digital Twins can simulate the impact of that development on traffic, public transport, the environment, and other aspects of urban life.

Figure 2 Conceptual Diagram of the network of interfaces and processes connected with Digital Twin Platforms and BIM

Furthermore, integrating real-time data into Digital Twins allows for **more efficient city management in emergency situations**. From managing natural disasters to coordinating massive events, Digital Twins provide decision-makers with a real-time view of the urban situation, facilitating a quick and coordinated response. In conclusion, BIM and the Digital Twins are playing a key role in the **transformation of our cities towards smarter, more resilient and sustainable urban environments**. These technologies not only improve efficiency and quality in the planning and construction of urban infrastructure, but also enable more efficient management and more informed decision-making in all aspects of urban life.

As we move towards an **increasingly digitised urban future**, it is crucial to harness the power of BIM and the Digital Twins to address the most pressing urban challenges, from mobility and land-use planning to resource management and disaster resilience. In doing so, we can build cities that are not only more efficient and liveable, but also more inclusive, **equitable and sustainable for generations to come**.

Building permits

BIM and building permitting

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is revolutionising urban planning and management by facilitating a **more collaborative and centralised working environment**. The main aspects and benefits of this methodology, as well as future changes in the administrative processes related to urban planning and building, are the following:

01

Information Centralisation

BIM allows the centralisation of all territorial and urban information in one place. This facilitates data access and management, ensuring that all project participants work with the same up-to-date information.

02

Element Parameterisation

With BIM, each architectural and urban element is modelled with parameters that can include data on dimensions, materials, costs, and more. This parameterisation helps to optimize designs and make modifications efficiently.

03

Optimization of Administrative Procedures

Optimize administrative procedures related to building and public works. This includes greater effectiveness and efficiency in processes, improvements in transparency, and an increase in the quality of architectural projects.

04

Data Uniqueness

BIM encourages the application of data uniqueness, which means that each piece of information is stored only once but is accessible to all involved, reducing errors and redundancies.

All this is leading to major changes in the Supervision and Documentation Processes

- 1. Transition from Manual to Digital:** Traditionally, the supervision of projects for obtaining planning permissions was done manually, using paper documents. However, with the implementation of the electronic administrative file, these processes are beginning to be digitised.
- 2. Adoption of Documentation in 2D Digital Format:** Currently, project documentation is presented in digital format, albeit mainly in 2D. This facilitates certain reviews but is still limited compared to the capabilities of BIM.
- 3. Integration of 3D BIM Models into Administrative Processes:** The future seems to be moving towards the integration of 3D models using BIM methodology into administrative processes. These models will include all the necessary information for the checking of urban planning regulations.
- 4. Use of Technological Tools for the Review of 3D Models:** 3D models can be reviewed using advanced technological tools, such as those developed in the [ACCORD project](#), containing the necessary planning parameters. This will allow a faster and more accurate verification of the compliance of projects with current regulations.

The implementation of BIM represents a **significant step towards the modernization of urban planning and management**. It not only improves the accuracy and efficiency of construction projects, but also promotes greater collaboration and transparency at all levels of urban planning. With the future incorporation of 3D modelling and technological review tools, licensing and regulatory compliance processes will become more streamlined and effective, benefiting both developers and regulatory authorities.

Digital twin and building permits

Integrating digital twins into the BIM methodology for model validation and integration with the urban environment further expands the capabilities of urban planning and management. Here I describe how these technological advances complement each other and the additional benefits they bring to the process:

01

Enhanced Validation

Digital twins enable real-time simulation and analysis of urban models, providing a platform for testing and validating designs prior to construction. By integrating DT with BIM models, planners can perform more comprehensive validations ranging from energy efficiency to environmental impact.

02

Real-Time Interaction with the Urban Environment

Digital twins continuously collect data through sensors and other IoT (Internet of Things) devices embedded in the urban environment. This allows BIM models to dynamically interact with real-world data, facilitating real-time adjustments to changing environmental conditions.

03

Complex Scenario Simulation

Using digital twins in conjunction with BIM allows complex scenarios such as natural disasters, traffic congestion, or mass events to be simulated. This is crucial for emergency response planning and optimisation of urban services.

04

Predictive Maintenance and Operations

The combination of BIM with digital twins not only helps in the design and construction phase, but also during the operation and maintenance of infrastructures. Digital twins can foresee potential problems and enable predictive maintenance, which reduces costs and improves the longevity of urban structures.

The benefits of Integration are:

- 1. Improved Decision Making:** Integration provides a richer and more detailed database that significantly improves decision making at all levels of urban management, from planning to operation and maintenance.
- 2. Efficiency and Cost Savings:** The ability to virtually simulate and validate projects prior to implementation can reduce construction costs and avoid costly mistakes. In addition, predictive maintenance minimises repair and maintenance costs.
- 3. Transparency and Citizen Participation:** Accurate modelling and real-time simulation foster greater transparency in urban projects. This can improve citizen trust and participation, allowing residents to better visualise and understand proposed changes to their environment.
- 4. Sustainability and Urban Resilience:** By anticipating how designs interact with the environment and respond to future events, digital twins and BIM together can lead to more sustainable planning and improved urban resilience.

The synergy between BIM and digital twins radically transforms the way cities are planned, built and managed. By integrating these systems, urban planners not only **optimise construction and administrative processes but also raise the level of interaction and adaptability of urban infrastructures with their environment, ensuring that cities are smarter, more sustainable and future-proof.**

BIM + Digital twins and building permitting

Combining 3D building modeling with digital twins adds the value of 3D to the permit process, which is done in the following steps:

Figure 3.- BIM + Digital twins and building permitting

1. The project developer places the Building Information Model (BIM) in a 3D environment, made digitally available by the municipality.

Using a digital twin in the 3D permit process means that the project developer creates a 3D Building Information Model, known as BIM. This model includes all project details, such as building dimensions, materials, installations, and other relevant aspects. Once completed, the 3D model is uploaded to a digital platform provided by the municipality, allowing all stakeholders to access the information accurately and up-to-date.

Advantages:

- Provides a clear and detailed visualization of the project.
- Facilitates communication between the developer and municipal authorities.
- Provides a solid base for analysis and decision-making.

2. Detection of conflicts between the Building Information Model, the substrate, and regulations.

Once the 3D model is digitally available, municipal authorities use advanced tools to detect possible conflicts. This can include issues with existing infrastructure, incompatibilities with the terrain (substrate), and violations of local regulations and standards. Conflict detection software can identify discrepancies and problems that might not be evident in traditional 2D plans.

Advantages:

- Identifies potential problems before construction begins.
- Reduces the risk of costly delays and modifications during construction.
- Ensures the project complies with all regulations and safety standards.

3. Adjustments and/or consultation.

After detecting conflicts, the next step is to make the necessary adjustments to the 3D model. This may involve modifying the design to resolve structural, environmental, or regulatory conflicts. It can also

involve additional consultations between the project developer, engineers, and municipal authorities to ensure all parties agree with the proposed modifications.

Advantages:

- Allows problems to be solved collaboratively and efficiently.
- Ensures all stakeholders are aligned and agree with the changes.
- Minimizes the possibility of errors and misunderstandings.

4. Appropriate design.

The final step is approving a final design that is appropriate and complies with all regulations and requirements detected in previous stages. This final design, now conflict-free, will guide the construction of the project. By resolving all problems beforehand, it ensures that construction can proceed without major interruptions.

Advantages:

- Ensures the final project is viable and compliant with regulations.
- Facilitates a smoother and problem-free construction process.
- Contributes to the sustainability and efficiency of the final project.

These four stages illustrate how integrating 3D models into the permit process not only improves accuracy and efficiency but also promotes closer collaboration and better project planning.

Strategies for Implementing Digital Twin for Digital Permits

Compliance Analysis is a cornerstone of utilizing digital technologies in the process of securing construction permits. In the digitization context, it refers to the systematic review of building plans and documents against regulatory codes and standards using digital tools. **The goal is to ensure that the proposed construction meets all the necessary legal and safety requirements before the actual construction begins.**

By employing digital twins and other digital models, we can automate the comparison of project specifications with the complex web of building regulations. This not only speeds up the process but also enhances accuracy, reducing the likelihood of human error. Additionally, it provides a **transparent record** that can be reviewed and audited, creating a clear trail of compliance that is essential for accountability.

In order to incorporate digital twins in the automation of planning permission processing using BIM methodology, it is necessary to establish certain **requirements and considerations** to ensure the effectiveness, efficiency, and transparency of the process. Below, I detail the key requirements for the effective implementation of digital twins in this context:

Interoperability with Urban Planning Tools

The digital twin must work with urban planning tools using open data formats and industry standards for smooth communication across different systems.

GIS Data Integration

Digital twins must integrate and process real-time data from other GIS to keep the digital model updated with the current site and environment conditions.

Automatic Updates and Change Management

Any changes in the project's design or parameters should automatically update in the digital twin, keeping all stakeholders informed for faster reviews and approvals.

Data Security and Privacy

Strong security and privacy measures are necessary to protect data managed by digital twins, including sensitive information, from unauthorized access and cyber threats.

Figure 4 Strategies for Implementing Digital Twin for Digital Permits

In this way, greater **transparency** is achieved in the process of validation of urban planning parameters, the uniqueness of the data, greater efficiency, and effectiveness in the urban planning process. However, the following requirements must be considered for the use of digital twins in this process.

Interoperable structure of software components

A **distributed, interoperable, open, open, federated, decentralised and scalable ecosystem** of Digital Twin and GIS applications is needed to facilitate the integration of multiple data sources and formats, designed by all for all. The following elements are to be considered

Digital Twins Interoperability Standard for Cities

ISO 19650 - Building Information Modeling (BIM)

Although ISO 19650 is traditionally used for building information modelling, BIM is being adapted for integration into digital city models. The EN ISO 19650 series consists of a set of standards:

- **ISO 19650-1** sets out the recommended concepts and principles for the development and management processes for information throughout the life cycle of any building asset.
- **ISO 19650-2** defines the processes for the development and management of information during the development phase.
- **ISO 19650-3** standard defines the processes for the use and management of information during the operation phase.
- **ISO 19650-4** defines the information exchange in BIM during the development and operation phases. This standard is currently under development.
- **ISO 19650-5** establishes the information security requirements.

ISO 19650 applies to projects and built assets of any size and level of complexity, but ISO 19650 recommends that its use is proportionate and appropriate. This should be taken into account especially in the case of projects or This should be especially taken into account in the case of small projects or assets and where the actors involved are SMEs. Proper application of the EN ISO 19650 series results in:

ISO/IEC 30173 - Digital twin, Concepts and terminology

The standard defines a digital twin as:

Digital representation of a target entity with data connections that enable convergence between the physical and digital states at an appropriate rate of synchronisation.

Where:

- **Target entity.** The target entity, simply put, is the subject of the digital twin. BS ISO/IEC 30173 describes these as being “real” things like components, assets, systems and processes. The subject is then observed through data connections like sensors.
- **Digital representation.** The digital representation is the digital version of one of the target entity. Depending on the subject, the way it is digitally represented may change. Much like with BIM, digital twins aren’t about 3D models; they are about the bi-directional exchange of pertinent information.
- **Convergence.** Convergence is the act of coming together. In this instance, convergence can be achieved in three different ways:
 - **The digital representation changes to reflect the target entity.** Example: A component, which is being tracked, is moved. Once in its new position, its location is updated with new coordinates.
 - **The target entity changes to reflect the digital representation.** Example: Someone sets a thermostat which is monitoring a living room; the thermostat triggers the room to warm up.
 - **Both the digital representation and target entity change to meet in the middle.** Example: A complex algorithm behind a series of interconnect digital twins may influence several entities and representations concurrently.

The idea that this convergence occurs as often as needed. For use cases relating to life safety, (near) real-time may be a requirement. However, for other use cases this convergence would happen less frequently.

CityGML

The **Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)** is playing a crucial role in the development of standards for digital twins, with the aim of establishing **standards** to ensure **interoperability** between different urban systems and platforms. This effort includes defining how data in digital twin models should be structured, exchanged and updated to facilitate their use in a variety of urban applications.

CityGML is an open standard developed by the OGC that **facilitates the exchange and storage of 3D urban geospatial data**. This model defines not only the physical structure of buildings but also their semantic characteristics, including the planning parameters required for urban planning permissions.

It is an open data model and XML standard for the storage and exchange of geometric and semantic data of cities and landscapes. CityGML is not only a format for 3D models, but also allows a semantic description and topology of urban structures.

By establishing **levels of information (LOI) and detail (LOD)**, CityGML allows urban planners and architects to use standardised nomenclatures and classifications, ensuring that the information is understandable and manageable across different platforms and software.

Figure 5.- CityGML levels. Delft University of Technology

Levels of developments are for BIM, related to the stage of design development, and intended to be replaced by Level of Information Need as per the new standard, which specifies the details of the information to be in the file more specifically.

The adoption of CityGML thus facilitates the creation of interoperable BIM models that integrate effectively with digital twins and urban parameter validation programmes.

IFC -Industry Foundation Classes

IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) is a data **format that allows the exchange of the information model** of an architectural or civil engineering project without the loss or distortion of the data it contains.

Regulated by **UNE-EN ISO 16739:2016**, it has been developed by **buildingSMART** according to the open BIM philosophy, which supports the realisation and operation of buildings and infrastructures through workflows and open standards.

IFC is being integrated into city modelling to ensure that buildings within urban models are detailed and managed efficiently and its use will soon be required in certain public contracts. The information in IFC is structured in:

- **Classes:** *These are typological groups of objects that have a certain function. For example, IfcWall, IfcLamp, IfcProject...*
- **Types:** *Each of the typological groups or subcategories to which they belong to a class, for example, IfcWallTypeEnum.PARTITIONING, IfcWallTypeEnum.PLUMBINGWALL*
- **Property Sets:** *a set or group of properties that have some kind of common relationship. E.g. Pset_SpaceCoveringRequirements.WallCovering*

Figure 6.- IFC Structure

Inspire

The INSPIRE (**I**nfra**S**tructure for **S**patial **I**nformation in **E**urope) Directive lays down the general rules for the establishment of an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community based on the Member States' infrastructures. Adopted by the European Parliament and the Council on 14 March 2007 (Directive 2007/2/EC), it entered into force on 25 April 2007.

This directive aims to create a spatial information infrastructure in Europe to **support environmental decision-making**. Although it focuses more on the environment, the data and models promoted are also applicable to urban modelling. In particular the following annexes, or themes, can provide standard

data modelling across Europe:

- In the **CadastralParcel** theme, the classes "CadastralZoning" and "ZoningElement" of the Planned Land Use module of the INSPIRE UML model serve to represent the cadastral information and the division of land into zones relevant for planning permission. It is necessary to extend the classes by adding some attributes that directly report the threshold parameters of some regulations (e.g. maximum allowed height of buildings, etc.).
- In the **Land Use theme**, the 'PlannedLandUse' module allows the storage of zoning geometry, at different levels, and its association to relevant regulations makes it suitable for storing zoning related to building permits and is flexible enough to adapt to different realities, i.e. different municipalities and national systems.

Moreover, it can be beneficial to allow the subdivision of ZoningElement, intended to cover the whole areas having similar regulations constraints, into smaller parts, representing the single plots, hosting the new projects. Plots, in turn, can include more than one cadastral parcel.

- The **Management, Restriction and Regulation Zones** theme, can be used to represent and identify areas that are subject to additional special regulations, especially for environmental reasons.
- **TNaturalRiskZone** and **ProtectedSite** are other parts of the INSPIRE data model that can be used to represent information relevant for extended building permits. ProtectedSite can also be used to represent protected cultural heritage areas and historic centres.

Data Spaces and Digital Twins in the European Context

In Europe, the concept of data spaces has become a key component of digital strategy, especially with the EU Data Strategy initiative. The European Common Data Spaces will facilitate access to and re-use of more data. This will be done in a trusted and secure environment for the benefit of European businesses and citizens.

Figure 7.- European Data Spaces

These data spaces are ecosystems in which data is ensured to be secure, accessible and usable by multiple actors across borders and sectors. Stakeholders drive the evolution of data spaces. Users in each sector contribute to shaping these spaces, resulting in the emergence of unique forms and characteristics. However, what underpins all European data spaces are common data infrastructures and governance frameworks, which facilitate data sharing, access and exchange. In addition, European Common Data Spaces have these key characteristics. They:

- Are **open to participation** by all organisations and individuals. Work is underway to provide controlled access to enable traceability and enforcement of rights.
- Have a **secure and privacy-preserving** infrastructure for pooling, accessing, sharing, processing and using data.
- Are a clear and practical structure for accessing and using data: the common european data space has fair, **transparent, proportionate and non-discriminatory access rules**, thanks to well-defined and reliable data governance mechanisms.
- Respect eu rules and values, especially personal and consumer data protection and competition law.
- Allow data subjects to **access** or **use** certain personal or **non-personal data**, controlling the public access with clear rules and specific conditions.
- **Empower data holders** to make data available for **re-use** free of charge or in return for compensation.

Integrating digital twins into these spaces enables cities and government entities to manage and analyse urban data more effectively, facilitating decision-making based on real-time information and predictive analytics. This approach not only improves urban governance but also drives innovation and sustainability in the development of urban infrastructure and services.

These standards are vital to ensure that digital city models are used effectively for testing building permit requirements, but also for urban simulations, sustainability analysis, development planning and much more.

Gis Data Integration

There is no single twin and each twin is built according to the needs and use cases for which it is required. The architecture that supports it and on which the Digital Twin is developed has to integrate and **integrate not only with the data and services it provides but also with the information external** to it, which may be provided by other agents or available in other areas, as well as the possibility of integrating other existing twins. The integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) data and digital twins enables the creation of highly detailed and dynamic digital representations of the physical world, facilitating **more accurate analysis and more informed decision making**.

What kind of information can be integrated?

Data integration in the context of GIS and digital twins involves combining geospatial data with data from other sources to create digital models that reflect the physical world with high accuracy. Geospatial data, which includes information about the location and characteristics of objects on Earth, can be summarised in these typologies

- **Sensory data:** Information collected from IoT (Internet of Things) sensors, which can include everything from temperature sensors to motion sensors and cameras.
- **Structural data:** Information on buildings, roads and other infrastructure, including their design specifications and materials.
- **Environmental data:** Climate, hydrographic and air quality information, which is crucial for urban planning and environmental management.
- **Demographic data:** Population information, such as density, age distribution, and mobility patterns.
- **Historical data:** Data that allows to see changes over time to understand trends and patterns.

Problems and Challenges

The integration of GIS data and digital twins is not without **technical** challenges:

- **Data heterogeneity:** Effective integration requires data from different sources and formats to be compatible and synchronised.
- **Large Data Volumes:** Handling large volumes of data in real time requires advanced computational capabilities and can lead to storage and processing issues.
- **Data Accuracy and Updating:** Maintaining data accuracy and updating data in continuously changing models is a constant challenge.

In addition to technical challenges, there are **organisational** and privacy concerns:

- **Data Governance:** The need for clear policies on who can access and control data. Establish clear and transparent data governance policies that define who can access data, how it can be used and shared, and how it will be protected.
- **Privacy:** The integration of detailed and personal data raises significant privacy and information security issues. Measures such as measures to protect data against unauthorised access and cyber-attacks will be necessary. And Privacy Awareness and Compliance to ensure that all processes comply with local and international privacy and data protection laws, such as GDPR in Europe.

The integration of GIS data with digital twins offers significant opportunities to improve decision making in many fields. However, technical, and organisational challenges require innovative solutions and collaboration across sectors and disciplines.

Automatic Updates and Change Management

Cities are dynamic entities, always moving and changing. If the data is old, the Digital Twin may reflect a reality that no longer exists. Therefore, it is crucial to understand **how often the data is updated** and whether that pace is sufficient to capture the dynamics of the city.

A digital twin is used by urban planners, governments and developers to analyse and forecast city behaviour in different scenarios. The recommendation on **how often to update** a digital city twin and how to ensure that it is up to date depends on several factors:

- **Significant Physical Changes:** It is recommended to update the digital twin after significant changes in the city's infrastructure, such as construction of new buildings, roads, or modification of transport systems.
- **Data Updates:** For dynamic data such as traffic, pollution, and service usage patterns, a real-time or at least daily update is recommended.
- **Planned Developments:** Before and after any planned urban development, the digital twin should be updated to reflect these planning modifications and their impact once completed.
- **Significant Events:** After significant events that may affect the infrastructure or functioning of the city, such as natural disasters, major public events or changes in legislation.

When it comes to ensuring that data is up to date, the strategy would be to integrate digital twins with data that allows changes to be known quickly, for example:

- **Sensor and IoT Integration:** Use Internet of Things (IoT) technologies and sensors distributed throughout the city to collect real-time data on various urban metrics.
- **Satellite Data Analysis:** For significant physical changes, use satellite imagery and geospatial analysis to update the 3D model of the city.
- **Institutional Collaboration:** Establish collaborations with government agencies, utilities and other stakeholders to obtain regular data updates that can influence the representation of the city.
- **User Feedback:** Incorporate a feedback mechanism where citizens can report changes or errors in the digital twin, ensuring a constant and participatory source of updates.
- **Automation and Machine Learning:** Implement machine learning systems that can predict changes in urban patterns and proactively update the digital twin based on these predictions.

Proper management of a digital city twin requires a multidisciplinary approach combining technology, urban planning and citizen participation. Keeping the digital twin up to date is essential to maximise its usefulness in urban planning and management.

Data Security and Privacy

Security in urban digital twins represents a fundamental challenge in the digital age, particularly when it comes to **handling sensitive and private data in urban environments**. Digital twins are virtual replicas of physical objects or systems that are used to simulate, monitor and predict the behaviour of their real counterparts. In an urban context, these digital twins can range from individual buildings to entire city infrastructures. Proper management of data security and privacy in these systems is critical for sustainability, operational efficiency and public trust. Among the challenges facing the urban digital twins are:

- **Volume and Variety of Data:** Urban digital twins integrate a huge amount of data from diverse sources such as IoT sensors, geographic information systems, and demographic data, among others. The diversity and volume of this data requires advanced management systems to ensure its integrity and security.
- **Data Access and Control:** Determining who has access to data and under what conditions is crucial to protect sensitive and personal information. Lack of adequate control can lead to security breaches and privacy violations.
- **Interoperability and Standards:** Digital twins must operate in a heterogeneous and often fragmented technology ecosystem, which requires high interoperability between different systems and platforms. The absence of uniform standards can increase the risk of incompatibilities and security vulnerabilities.
- **Upgrades and Maintenance:** The technology underpinning the digital twins needs constant maintenance and upgrades to protect against new vulnerabilities and cyber-attacks. Neglect in this regard can leave critical systems exposed to security risks.

To address these challenges, a framework for developing a secure infrastructure for urban digital twins is proposed:

- **Data identification and classification:** It is crucial to identify and classify data by its content, use and potential users, thus establishing classification levels based on the sensitivity and impact a security breach could have on this data.
- **Encryption and Data Security:** Implement high-level encryption for all stored and transmitted data. Encryption should be complemented by other security technologies, such as firewalls and intrusion detection and prevention systems.
- **Identity and Access Management:** Use robust identity and access management (IAM) systems to ensure that only authorised users can access sensitive data. This includes multi-factor authentication and granular role-based access control.
- **Constant Auditing and Monitoring:** Establish regular audit procedures and real-time monitoring systems to identify and respond to suspicious or malicious activity. This will help prevent data breaches and quickly mitigate any security issues that arise.

- **Legal and Compliance Framework:** Ensure that all digital twin operations comply with local and international data protection and privacy laws and regulations. This includes in the European context:
 - **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):** This is the main framework for data protection in Europe, regulating the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data.
 - **Data Governance Act (DGA) Regulation:** This regulates the re-use of certain categories of data held by public sector bodies and sets conditions for the re-use of data protected by commercial confidentiality, statistics, intellectual property rights or personal data.
 - **Data Act Regulation (Data Act):** Complements the DGA and extends access rights to non-personal data, devoting specific sections to essential requirements for interoperability in data spaces.
 - **Digital Markets Regulation and Digital Services Regulation:** These regulate digital markets and services, establishing harmonised rules on the provision of intermediary services in the internal market and basic platform services offered by Access Guardians.
 - **Regulation on the Free Movement of Non-Personal Data:** This sets out guidelines for the free movement of non-personal data in the European Union.
- **Incident response and data recovery:** Develop incident response plans to effectively manage and mitigate any threats, ensuring business continuity through robust backup and recovery plans.
- **Education and Awareness:** Train all system users, from developers to end-users, on security and privacy best practices. Awareness can significantly reduce the risk of human error that can compromise security.

Urban digital twins have the potential to transform the management of cities and significantly improve the quality of life of their inhabitants. However, the successful implementation of these systems depends heavily on their ability to manage data security and privacy effectively. By adopting a comprehensive approach that includes advanced technology, sound management practices, and a clear legal framework, **it is possible to create an infrastructure that is not only effective but also secure and respectful of individuals' privacy.**

Uses cases

In the following sections, we will enumerate a **series of use cases** that highlight the integration of digital twins and Building Information Modeling (BIM). These use cases demonstrate how combining these advanced technologies can enhance various aspects of construction, real estate management, and urban planning. By leveraging the power of digital twins and BIM, organizations can achieve greater accuracy, efficiency, and insight in their projects.

Use Case 1: Automated Regulatory Compliance Validation through Digital Twin in Building Permit Workflows

The issuance of building permits constitutes a critical stage in the life cycle of any construction project. Traditionally, this process has relied on manual evaluations, subjective interpretation of planning documents, and heterogeneous data formats. The integration of Building Information Modeling (BIM) with Digital Twin (DT) platforms—enriched with geospatial context and machine-readable planning regulations—enables a transition towards a semi-automated, traceable, and legally accountable regulatory workflow.

This use case outlines a digitally enabled approach to automate the review of proposed building models against zoning and construction regulations using an architecture that combines BIM, GIS, and semantic rule-checking mechanisms.

Operational Scenario

The process begins when a municipal inspector receives a digital request for a construction permit. This request includes a building model submitted in **IFC 4.3** format, containing both geometric and semantic attributes of the proposed development.

The model is uploaded into a Digital Twin platform operating in a 3D, interoperable environment. The platform automatically aligns the BIM model with contextual geospatial datasets, including cadastral boundaries, zoning classifications, protected areas, and environmental constraints. These data are typically served via standard OGC services (e.g., WFS, CityGML) and allow the project to be precisely geolocated and assessed in relation to its surroundings.

Once the model is contextualized, a **regulatory validation engine** is triggered. This engine applies a set of formally encoded rules—represented using SHACL, RDF, or SPARQL queries—over both the BIM objects and their spatial relationships. The engine evaluates compliance with constraints such as maximum building height, setback distances, allowable land use, and buffer zones around sensitive areas.

The system then generates a structured report indicating whether the proposal complies with the applicable regulations. If conflicts are detected, the system visualizes the violations within the 3D interface and provides rule-based justifications for each non-compliance, streamlining resolution and improving administrative transparency.

System Architecture

The proposed system is built upon a federated digital infrastructure comprising:

- A **BIM kernel**, where building data are structured in **IFC 4.3**, enriched with property sets (Psets) relevant to zoning and building code verification.
- A **normative knowledge base**, where urban regulations are formalized using semantic web technologies such as SHACL or OWL, enabling rule reasoning and traceability.

- A **geospatial data subsystem**, delivering context-aware data layers (e.g., cadastral parcels, zoning areas, transport networks, protected sites) exposed through OGC-compliant APIs and INSPIRE-compliant schemas.
- A **semantic validation engine**, capable of performing rule-based reasoning across BIM and GIS datasets to determine regulatory compliance.
- A **3D visualization interface**, powered by web technologies (e.g., CesiumJS), allowing stakeholders to inspect the model, understand conflicts, and track compliance status interactively.

Types of Validatable Constraints

The system supports automated validation of various regulatory constraints, which fall into three broad categories:

- **Geometric constraints**, such as maximum building height, floor area ratio, building footprint coverage, and required setbacks. These are directly derived from measurable geometric attributes of the BIM model.
- **Functional constraints**, related to the compatibility of building use (e.g., residential, commercial, industrial) with the designated land use zoning. These rules require cross-referencing BIM space/function classifications with zoning layers.
- **Relational constraints**, which evaluate spatial relationships between the project and its surroundings—e.g., minimum distances to protected structures, rights-of-way, road access conditions, or impact on infrastructure or environmental zones.

Implementation Requirements and Expected Benefits

Effective implementation of this system requires:

- Availability of detailed and semantically enriched **IFC models**
- A formalized **digital representation of planning regulations**
- Access to **authoritative, up-to-date geospatial datasets**
- Deployment of a Digital Twin platform with **interoperability mechanisms and semantic querying capabilities**

The primary benefits include a significant reduction in administrative processing times, improved objectivity and consistency in permit decisions, and enhanced traceability and auditability. Moreover, the approach fosters public trust through transparency and facilitates stakeholder collaboration by enabling shared 3D visualization and feedback mechanisms.

Use Case 2: Semantic Verification of Space Modeling through BIM-GIS Integration in Digital Twin Environments

Accurate spatial modeling is a prerequisite for reliable regulatory validation, performance analysis, and digital permitting processes. Errors in the definition of spaces—such as misaligned boundaries, incorrect volumes, or omitted classifications—can compromise rule-checking automation, energy simulations, and urban compatibility assessments. Within the Digital Twin (DT) framework, a systematic approach to verify and validate spatial definitions ensures that each component of the digital building model is accurately modeled, semantically complete, and aligned with its physical and legal context.

This use case presents a methodology for automating the verification of internal and external space definitions in Building Information Models (BIM), with spatial alignment to cadastral and zoning data via GIS integration.

Operational Scenario

During a digital building permit review, an inspector accesses the submitted **IFC model** through a DT-based platform. The system initiates a **space validation routine**, wherein it parses and classifies all spatial entities within the model (e.g., IfcSpace, IfcZone, IfcBuildingStorey), assessing their geometric integrity and semantic completeness.

In parallel, the DT platform retrieves GIS data layers representing the cadastral unit, surrounding infrastructure, and applicable regulatory envelopes. Through spatial overlay operations, the system checks whether modeled spaces align with:

- The legally defined parcel boundaries,
- Permissible building envelopes (setbacks, heights),
- Functional zones (e.g., service areas, common/shared spaces).

Each space is evaluated both geometrically (position, size, contiguity) and semantically (usage type, code compliance, required properties). The system flags anomalies such as overlapping spaces, invalid volume calculations, or missing functional annotations. This results in a comprehensive diagnostic report that supports early correction and reduces downstream validation failures.

System Architecture

The verification process is enabled by the following technical components:

- A **semantic parsing engine** that extracts and classifies spaces from IFC models, mapping them to formal definitions based on building codes and permitting regulations.
- A **geospatial data broker** that provides reference layers for cadastral boundaries, zoning overlays, and external constraints, ensuring spatial alignment.
- A **compliance validation module** that evaluates geometric consistency (e.g., space adjacency, enclosure, duplication) and compares functional annotations against predefined typologies (e.g., residential, commercial, circulation).
- A **ruleset library**, structured using SHACL or SWRL, that encodes space modeling rules and constraints based on national and local regulations.
- A **visualization dashboard** allowing real-time inspection of space definitions, highlighting issues and providing suggestions for correction.

Evaluation Criteria and Types of Checks

The system performs multiple levels of spatial validation, including:

- **Geometric consistency checks:** Verifying that each space is fully enclosed, does not overlap with adjacent spaces, and matches expected dimensional tolerances.
- **Topological relationships:** Ensuring spaces are connected logically (e.g., circulation paths, vertical continuity across stories), using spatial graphs derived from BIM geometry.
- **Semantic integrity:** Checking that spaces are labeled with appropriate functions (e.g., IfcSpaceType), required property sets (e.g., Pset_SpaceCommon), and align with the designated use as per the zoning layer.
- **Zonal conformance:** Validating that internal spatial configurations adhere to regulations concerning occupancy, service ratios, ventilation areas, etc., especially for residential or public buildings.

Implementation Requirements and Impact

Successful deployment requires well-structured IFC models with complete space definitions, compliant with ISO 16739 and enriched with typological metadata. In addition, accurate GIS datasets must be available to establish geospatial context and to facilitate overlay validation.

The integration of this validation process into a DT platform contributes to:

- Early-stage error detection in space modeling,
- Increased automation in digital permit workflows,
- Reduced regulatory rejections due to spatial inconsistencies,
- Improved model quality and trust in data for downstream simulations (e.g., energy, safety).

Furthermore, by leveraging semantic web technologies, the framework ensures extensibility across jurisdictions and supports alignment with both building performance metrics and spatial planning requirements.

Use Case 3: Real-Time Monitoring of Cast-In-Place Reinforced Concrete Structures Using Digital Twin Technology

This use case describes the implementation of a **Digital Twin (DT)** to support the real-time monitoring of a cast-in-place reinforced concrete building during the construction phase. The goal is to link as-designed models, field-collected data, and temporal execution events in a unified digital environment that enables continuous comparison between planned and actual progress, detection of deviations, and proactive decision-making on-site.

Operational Scenario

During construction, the project team deploys a DT platform that receives two main data sources:

1. An **as-designed BIM model**, structured in IFC format, providing geometry and semantic metadata (dimensions, materials, systems, components, construction phases).
2. A continuous flow of **as-built data** collected from the field, including:
 - 3D point clouds from laser scanning to capture actual geometry.
 - IoT sensor streams monitoring temperature, humidity, and ambient conditions.
 - Georeferenced images and videos documenting site progress.

The DT system synchronizes these inputs through a middleware engine that maps real-time construction events to the planned 4D timeline. It allows the project team to inspect the current state of execution against design intent and schedule, visually identify deviations, and support quality control. Results are displayed via interactive dashboards and 3D viewers accessible to contractors, supervisors, and project managers.

System Architecture

The technical components of the DT-based construction monitoring system include:

- **As-Designed Model Layer:** A BIM model in IFC 4.3 format, structured by construction phase and enriched with spatial and functional metadata.
- **As-Built Capture Module:** Field data inputs from laser scanners, environmental sensors, and site cameras.
- **Synchronization Engine:** A middleware that matches field events to the 4D construction schedule using rule-based scripts and timestamped logs.

- **Data Storage and Alignment:** Unified data environment for integrating and comparing as-designed and as-built states.
- **Visualization Interface:** Web and/or AR-based dashboards allowing progress review, deviation alerts, and issue annotation.

Validation Criteria and Supported Functions

Function	Technical Implementation
Geometric Comparison	Point cloud-to-IFC alignment to detect physical discrepancies and dimensional outliers
Progress Tracking	Time-based synchronization of construction events with 4D planning sequences
Quality Traceability	Environmental condition logging during execution and tolerance verification
Error Detection	Algorithmic detection of misalignment, missing elements, or delayed tasks
Decision Support	Real-time dashboards for monitoring, issue tracking, and construction management oversight

Implementation Requirements and Impact

Requirements

- A high-fidelity BIM model structured by task and phase.
- On-site deployment of 3D scanning and IoT sensor infrastructure.
- A DT platform capable of time-based comparison and spatial analytics.

Expected Benefits

- Reduced rework due to early deviation detection.
- Stronger linkage between digital design and physical execution.
- Streamlined construction management through transparent monitoring.
- Digital audit trail for certification, handover, and dispute resolution.

Use Case 4: Automated Validation of Setbacks and Alignments Using a Digital Twin for Building Permit Applications

Ensuring compliance with **setbacks** (minimum distances from property boundaries, public roads, or adjacent buildings) and **mandatory alignments** (e.g., façade lines) is a common and critical requirement in building permitting workflows. Manual validation through 2D drawings often leads to errors and ambiguities—especially in dense urban areas or irregular plots.

This use case describes how a **Digital Twin (DT)** platform can automate the validation of spatial constraints such as setbacks and alignments, by integrating BIM models, cadastral and planning GIS data, and formalized urban regulations.

Operational Scenario

As part of the digital building permit application, the applicant uploads a **georeferenced IFC model** of the proposed building to the municipal platform. This model is automatically linked with:

- Official **parcel boundaries** (e.g., INSPIRE CadastralParcel or GML),
- **Mandatory alignment lines** from urban plans (street frontage, zoning envelopes),

- **Zoning regulations** applicable to the parcel (based on zone, subzone, or land use),
- The **urban context**, including neighboring structures and easements.

The DT platform automatically identifies the building envelope and calculates the shortest distances from each face of the proposed structure to parcel boundaries and street axes. It verifies whether required setbacks are respected in each direction.

If violations are detected, the system generates a visual 3D report highlighting the conflict zones and referencing the applicable regulatory articles. If the model is compliant, the system issues an automated validation, allowing the permit workflow to advance to the next stage.

System Architecture

The technical setup includes:

- A **georeferenced BIM model** (IFC with Local Placement transformed to a real-world CRS, e.g., EPSG).
- A **spatial analysis module** to compute distances from the building geometry to cadastral and planning boundaries.
- A **semantic rule base** (SHACL or OWL) representing setback and alignment rules defined in urban codes.
- A **3D viewer interface** for visual inspection and generation of annotated compliance reports.
- A **rule-checking engine** with configurable tolerances and full legal traceability.

Types of Constraints Evaluated

- **Front setback:** distance to the designated alignment or street line.
- **Lateral and rear setbacks:** distances to neighboring parcels or rear plot limits.
- **Proximity to existing buildings**, whether on or outside the parcel.
- **Use-specific constraints**, e.g., for inner courtyards, public facilities, or corner lots.
- **Alignment validation:** ensuring the proposed building follows the mandatory urban façade line.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- Properly georeferenced IFC models or transformed to a spatial reference system (e.g., EPSG:25830).
- Digitalized and formalized zoning codes and setback rules.
- Access to cadastral, planning, and regulatory data in GIS (CityGML, GeoJSON, or GML).
- A DT platform capable of combining spatial geometry with rule-based validation.

Benefits

- Eliminates subjective interpretation of 2D drawings.
- Significantly reduces review time for geometric compliance.
- Enables legally traceable, consistent, and reproducible decisions.
- Integrates seamlessly with automated Digital Building Permit workflows.
- Increases transparency for designers, reviewers, and the public.

Use Case 5: Automated Verification of Sunlight Access and Shadow Compliance Using a Digital Twin for Building Permits

Urban regulations often include requirements related to **sunlight exposure** for habitable spaces and **shadow casting** onto adjacent parcels or buildings. These criteria are especially relevant in dense urban environments, where courtyard dimensions, building heights, and façade orientation critically affect access to daylight and thermal comfort.

This use case describes how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automatically assess compliance with solar exposure and shading conditions, using georeferenced BIM models, 3D urban context data, and simulation of solar paths, in line with planning regulations.

Operational Scenario

As part of the digital permit application, the project team uploads a **georeferenced BIM model** of the proposed building. The DT platform integrates:

- A **3D model of the surrounding urban environment**, including nearby buildings, terrain, and open spaces.
- **Solar position data** (based on latitude, orientation, date, and time), either embedded or dynamically computed.
- **Applicable regulatory requirements**, typically defined as:
 - Minimum hours of direct sunlight on habitable room windows.
 - Minimum sunlight exposure in courtyards or patios.
 - Restrictions on projected shadows affecting neighboring buildings or parcels.

The DT executes **solar simulations** at critical times of the year (equinoxes, solstices), generating shadow maps and sunlight duration visualizations. It then compares these results to regulatory thresholds to determine compliance.

System Architecture

The technical system includes:

- A **BIM model** with clearly defined openings (IfcWindow, IfcOpening) and habitable spaces (IfcSpace).
- A **3D contextual model** of the surrounding urban area, generated from GIS data, CityGML, or point clouds.
- A **solar simulation engine**, capable of calculating solar angles and shadow projections in 3D over time.
- A **normative rule base** (RDF, SHACL) encoding required sunlight conditions based on building type, orientation, or urban classification.
- A **visual analysis dashboard**, displaying shadow maps, sunlight durations per surface, and compliance indicators.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Minimum sunlight duration** for habitable rooms, as required by zoning regulations.
- **Surface percentage receiving daylight** in internal courtyards, terraces, or collective spaces.
- **Shadow impact on neighboring buildings**, evaluated for key hours or seasonal thresholds.
- **Verification of daylight access rights** for both self-owned and adjacent properties.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- A detailed and accurately georeferenced BIM model with semantic definition of spaces and openings.
- A 3D model of the surrounding built environment.
- A validated solar simulation engine suited for urban-scale modeling.
- Access to formalized planning regulations regarding sunlight and shading conditions.

Benefits

- Automated validation of health, comfort, and solar access criteria.
- Prevention of legal disputes related to shadow impact on neighboring plots.
- Early-stage design feedback to resolve daylighting issues proactively.
- Significant efficiency gains for permit approvals in high-density urban settings.
- Supports broader environmental and climate-resilience assessments.

Use Case 6: Automated Validation of Accessibility Requirements Using a Digital Twin in the Building Permit Process

Compliance with **universal accessibility regulations** is mandatory in most European countries for new constructions, major renovations, and public spaces. Manual verification of slopes, clear widths, turning radii, and accessible routes using 2D drawings can be error-prone and inefficient. By integrating BIM models with machine-readable regulations, a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automate this process, ensuring objective, traceable, and reproducible validation.

Operational Scenario

During the technical review phase of a building permit application, the BIM model is uploaded to a DT platform. The platform automatically extracts relevant architectural and spatial elements such as:

- **Doors, corridors, ramps, stairs, elevators** (IfcDoor, IfcRamp, IfcStair, IfcSpace, IfcBuildingStorey).
- **Public-use and mandatory-access spaces.**
- **Topological relationships** among spaces (connectivity, continuity, level transitions).

A set of accessibility rules—encoded using formal logic (e.g., SHACL)—is then applied to validate:

- Minimum **clear width** of doors and circulation routes.
- **Ramp slope and length**, including requirements for intermediate landings.
- **Turning radius** in common areas and sanitary facilities.
- Existence and continuity of an **accessible route** from the public sidewalk to interior spaces.
- **Location and specifications of accessible toilets** in required zones.

System Architecture

The DT-based accessibility validation system includes:

- A **detailed BIM model**, with relevant accessibility attributes stored in IFC property sets (e.g., Pset_DoorCommon, Pset_RampCommon).
- A **formal rule base** or ontology adapted to national or local accessibility regulations.

- A **validation engine** capable of traversing the spatial graph of the building and detecting non-conformities.
- An **interactive 3D viewer** that highlights detected violations with visual markers and semantic annotations.
- A **machine-readable validation report**, which can be archived in the digital building permit dossier.

Types of Constraints Evaluated

- **Minimum widths and heights** for circulation elements (corridors, doors, elevators).
- **Maximum allowable slopes** for ramps, with required landing dimensions.
- **Continuity of the accessible path**, without barriers or unaddressed level changes.
- **Presence and correct layout of accessible toilets** for public-use zones.
- **Accessible entry points** from public roads or sidewalks into the building.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- An IFC model with well-structured spatial and functional components.
- Accessibility codes available in machine-readable formats (SHACL, RDF, OWL).
- A DT platform capable of spatial reasoning and graph traversal.

Benefits

- **Reduces post-permit compliance issues** by identifying violations early in design.
- **Enables objective and standardized validation**, minimizing subjective interpretation.
- **Supports review of complex buildings** with multiple access points and levels.
- **Enhances legal transparency and traceability** within the permitting process.
- **Promotes social inclusion and regulatory compliance** from the design phase.

Use Case 7: Automated Verification of Zoning Use Compliance Using a Digital Twin in Building Permit Workflows

One of the fundamental checks in any building permit process is determining whether the **intended use of the proposed building** (residential, commercial, industrial, institutional, etc.) is **compatible with the applicable zoning regulations**. Traditionally, this task involves manually reviewing urban planning documents and zoning tables—a process that is time-consuming, error-prone, and difficult to scale.

This use case describes how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform**, integrating BIM data, zoning layers, and structured regulations, can automate this compliance check reliably and transparently.

Operational Scenario

During the submission of a building permit application, the project team provides a **BIM model (IFC)** that classifies the functional use of each space or unit (e.g., residential unit, retail space, office, garage, warehouse).

The DT platform performs the following:

- **Geolocates the building** and identifies the applicable **zoning category or subzone** based on the parcel's coordinates (retrieved from current urban planning datasets).

- Loads the **zoning regulation** associated with the zone, including permitted, conditional, and prohibited uses.
- Compares the **proposed building uses** in the BIM model with those allowed in the zoning regulation.

If the proposed use is non-compliant, the system issues a warning and generates a traceable report referencing the applicable article or zoning table. If the use is allowed, an automated compliance certificate is generated for the permit dossier.

System Architecture

- **IFC 4.3 BIM model**, with semantic classification of spaces using IfcSpace, IfcBuildingStorey, and property sets defining intended use.
- **GIS-based zoning layers**, stored in interoperable formats such as CityGML, GeoJSON, or INSPIRE LandUse datasets.
- **Formalized regulatory knowledge base**, associating each zone code with its list of permitted and restricted uses (e.g., RDF or SHACL).
- **Semantic validation engine**, comparing proposed uses with the rule set for the identified zone.
- **Compliance viewer**, allowing users to explore zoning overlays, applicable constraints, and compliance status with automated report generation.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Primary use compliance** (e.g., residential building in a residential zone).
- **Mixed-use compliance** (e.g., retail on ground floor of residential buildings).
- **Exclusion of prohibited uses** (e.g., industrial functions in protected urban zones).
- **Maximum allowable surface per use**, if regulated (e.g., commercial space limited to 40% of total GFA).
- **Associated requirements** (e.g., required parking spaces per use type).

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- BIM model with detailed, semantically structured space use definitions.
- Up-to-date, georeferenced zoning datasets.
- Digitized and machine-readable urban planning regulations.
- A DT platform that supports BIM-GIS semantic interoperability.

Benefits

- **Minimizes rejections due to zoning incompatibility** at the early design stage.
- **Reduces workload for municipal reviewers** by automating a repetitive but essential task.
- **Ensures traceability and transparency** in zoning compliance evaluations.
- **Improves the designer's ability to comply early**, enabling proactive project adjustments.
- **Scales well for batch validations** or city-wide zoning enforcement audits.

Use Case 8: Automated Verification of Maximum Site Occupation and Buildable Area Using a Digital Twin in Urban Building Permits

Urban zoning regulations typically define strict limits on:

- **Maximum ground-level occupation** (percentage of the parcel covered by the building's footprint),
- **Maximum buildable floor area** (total square meters allowed per square meter of parcel surface).

Validating these parameters is essential for ensuring regulatory compliance, urban equity, and sustainable development. This use case describes how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform**, integrating BIM models and zoning datasets, can automatically verify whether a proposed building complies with occupation and floor area ratio (FAR) limits as part of a digital building permit workflow.

Operational Scenario

The applicant submits a **georeferenced IFC model** of the proposed building, with elements structured by story and use. The DT platform performs the following steps:

- Identifies construction elements in contact with the ground (e.g., IfcBuilding, IfcSlab, IfcSpace).
- Calculates the **ground-level footprint** and the **total constructed floor area** (per floor and overall).
- Retrieves the applicable urban zoning rules based on parcel location and zoning code.
- Compares computed values against **maximum permitted thresholds** for site occupation (%) and buildable area (FAR in m²/m²).

If any violations are found, the system generates an automated report with referenced zoning articles, tolerance margins, and a 3D visualization of the affected areas. If the design is compliant, a digital certificate of conformity is issued.

System Architecture

- **IFC-compliant BIM model**, with spatial elements organized by floor, usage, and measured surface.
- **Cadastral and zoning GIS datasets**, including parcel boundaries and zoning codes.
- **Formalized regulatory rule base**, defining limits and formulas per zoning designation.
- **Surface calculation engine**, capable of computing area ratios based on geometry and classification.
- **Compliance viewer**, displaying results, visual alerts, and downloadable reports with full traceability.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Ground-floor footprint area**, expressed as a percentage of parcel surface.
- **Total buildable floor area**, compared to allowed Floor Area Ratio (FAR).
- **Detection of overbuilt volumes** extending beyond permitted boundaries (e.g., projections, annexes).
- **Validation by use type**, where zoning applies different coefficients for residential, commercial, or mixed-use buildings.
- **Volumetric consistency checks**, where complementary parameters such as height or setbacks also apply.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- Accurate and georeferenced BIM model with defined geometry, usage, and surface attributes.
- Up-to-date zoning and cadastral datasets in interoperable GIS formats.
- DT platform with surface computation capabilities and linked zoning logic.

Benefits

- **Eliminates manual area calculations** and misinterpretation of zoning formulas.
- **Reduces permit rejections and rework** due to overbuilding or FAR violations.
- **Provides traceable and auditable reports** for both authorities and applicants.
- **Supports automated generation of urban development capacity certificates.**
- **Integrates seamlessly with volumetric and geometric validation modules** in the DT platform.

Use Case 9: Automated Validation of Minimum Parking Provision Using a Digital Twin in the Building Permit Process

Many urban planning regulations require a **minimum number of parking spaces** based on the intended use of a building, its total floor area, or the number of functional units (e.g., dwellings, offices, retail units). Verifying this manually—especially in mixed-use buildings or those with shared parking arrangements—can be time-consuming and error-prone.

This use case demonstrates how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automate the validation of parking requirements by cross-referencing BIM data with structured zoning regulations and parcel information from GIS.

Operational Scenario

The applicant submits an **IFC model** of the proposed building, which includes explicitly defined and classified parking spaces (e.g., IfcSpace with use = "Parking" or IfcParking), as well as the number of units or floor area per use category.

The DT platform then:

- Automatically identifies all parking spaces and classifies them by type (vehicle, accessible, bicycle).
- Retrieves applicable zoning rules for the parcel, such as minimum ratios (e.g., 1 space per 100 m² or per dwelling).
- Computes the required number of parking spaces by use, level, and type.
- Compares the required and provided quantities and generates a compliance or non-compliance report.

System Architecture

- A **structured BIM model**, with semantic classification of space usage and geometry (IfcSpace, IfcBuildingStorey, Psets).
- A **digitized parking regulation rule set**, defined per land use, building type, and urban zone.
- A **counting and logic validation module**, capable of detecting functional units and applying proportional calculations.
- A **visual reporting engine**, generating automatic reports and highlighting modeled parking areas.
- **Optional GIS integration** to validate site access, distances to public roadways, or integration with transportation nodes.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Minimum number of spaces** required per dwelling, floor area, or use type.
- **Required distribution of space types** (e.g., accessible spaces, bicycle parking).
- **Mandatory location constraints** (e.g., basement, ground floor, exterior).
- **Accessibility compliance**, including proximity to entrances and integration with accessible paths.
- **Validation of shared or rotational use spaces**, if allowed by local codes.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- A correctly classified and semantically enriched IFC model with defined spaces and surface areas.
- Digitized zoning rules in machine-readable form (e.g., SHACL, JSON-LD).
- A DT platform with semantic reasoning and functional unit detection capabilities.

Benefits

- **Avoids under- or over-provisioning** of parking during early design stages.
- **Increases transparency and consistency** in technical review processes.
- **Simplifies review of complex buildings** with shared, mixed-use, or rotational parking.
- **Enables traceability and reuse of parking data** for asset management, mobility planning, and smart parking systems.
- **Aligns building design with broader sustainable mobility goals** and city planning strategies.

Use Case 10: Automated Verification of Legal Easement Compliance Using a Digital Twin in Building Permit Processes

Administrative easements (e.g., related to roads, railways, airspace, coastal zones, water bodies, heritage sites) impose constraints on land use and construction due to safety, environmental, or legal obligations. These restrictions often stem from **sectoral regulations** rather than urban zoning codes, making them difficult to identify and verify manually during the permitting process.

This use case shows how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automatically detect whether a proposed project falls within easement-affected areas and assess its compliance with the associated legal constraints, by integrating BIM data with official geospatial datasets.

Operational Scenario

The applicant submits a **georeferenced BIM model** of the proposed development. The DT platform performs the following:

- Automatically overlays the model with **official GIS layers** that define protected or constrained areas (e.g., road protection zones, riverbanks, airport zones, electrical corridors, cultural heritage areas).
- Detects whether the project intersects or encroaches upon any easement zone.
- Retrieves the regulatory conditions associated with the affected easement (e.g., no construction allowed, height limits, setback requirements, terrain alteration bans).
- Compares the building's geometry with the easement restrictions and generates a compliance report.

System Architecture

- A **georeferenced IFC model** (version 4.3 or higher), with accurate geometry and elevation data.
- A **set of sectoral GIS layers**, provided by relevant authorities (e.g., ministries, water agencies, cultural heritage departments).
- A **spatial analysis engine**, capable of calculating intersections, distances, and volumetric intrusions.
- A **digital easement rule catalog**, structured by type, jurisdiction, and applicable constraints.

- A **legal traceability module**, linking each restriction to its official regulatory source and documentation.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Presence detection**: whether the parcel or project lies within an easement zone.
- **Condition checks**, including:
 - Minimum distance from rivers or natural watercourses.
 - Maximum height near power lines, airports, or radar systems.
 - Prohibition of ground alteration in archaeological or protected zones.
 - Requirement of pre-approval by sectoral authorities (e.g., aviation, environment).
- **Volumetric analysis**, including projections such as overhangs, balconies, or underground elements.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- Georeferenced BIM model with precise geometry and semantic data.
- Access to up-to-date, standardized easement layers (e.g., WFS, GeoJSON, GML).
- Digital catalog of easement rules and regulatory references.
- DT platform with 3D spatial analysis and legal compliance features.

Benefits

- **Prevents critical errors** that could invalidate a permit post-approval.
- **Reduces reliance on manual expert checks** for sector-specific regulations.
- **Centralizes multisource legal constraints** into a unified validation environment.
- **Enhances legal certainty** and minimizes regulatory risk during design.
- **Streamlines requests for mandatory sectoral reports**, when applicable.

Use Case 11: Automated Validation of Minimum Building Separation Distances Using a Digital Twin in Construction Permitting

Many urban planning regulations impose **minimum separation distances between buildings** to ensure adequate ventilation, natural lighting, privacy, and fire safety. These distances may apply to buildings within the same parcel or in relation to neighboring structures.

This use case describes how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automatically validate such spatial constraints by integrating BIM models, 3D data of the built environment, and structured zoning regulations.

Operational Scenario

During the submission of a building permit application, the applicant provides a **georeferenced BIM model** of the proposed construction. The DT platform then:

- Extracts the **building volume geometry** (IfcBuilding, IfcWall, IfcSlab, etc.).
- Retrieves a **3D model of the surrounding built environment**, such as CityGML (LoD2+), municipal GIS, or laser scans.
- Calculates the **horizontal distance** between the proposed building and all surrounding structures, whether internal (same parcel) or external (adjacent parcels).

- Loads the **applicable planning regulations**, which define required minimum distances based on building use, height, or zoning category.
- Compares computed distances to required thresholds and generates a **compliance report** with 3D visualizations and regulatory references.

System Architecture

- A **georeferenced IFC model** with accurate 3D volumetry of the proposed building.
- A **3D context model** of the urban fabric (from CityGML, point clouds, or existing GIS data).
- A **structured rule base** specifying minimum separation distances (e.g., 3 m between residential facades, 6 m for institutional blocks).
- A **3D spatial analysis engine**, capable of measuring envelope-to-envelope distances.
- A **visual inspection interface**, highlighting violations and citing relevant zoning articles.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Minimum facade-to-facade distances**, to ensure light and privacy.
- **Internal separation between independent building blocks** within the same parcel.
- **Clearances to adjacent buildings**, even if they belong to a different owner or project.
- **Differentiated thresholds by use, height, or zone type** (e.g., greater separations for schools or hospitals).
- **Conditional exceptions**, such as reduced distances if no openings are present or if building height is limited.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- An accurately georeferenced BIM model (IFC) with full volumetric detail.
- A spatially aligned 3D context model of surrounding buildings.
- Digitized urban regulations defining separation rules in machine-readable form.
- A DT platform with 3D measurement and semantic validation capabilities.

Benefits

- **Prevents future legal disputes** with neighbors or planning authorities.
- **Identifies spatial conflicts early in the design process**, reducing rework.
- **Automates a complex normative spatial check**, enhancing efficiency and consistency.
- **Generates clear, visual reports** for use by architects, reviewers, and citizens.
- **Promotes more coherent and livable urban environments** through enforceable spacing rules.

Use Case 12: Automated Verification of Natural Hazard Exposure and Design Adaptation Using a Digital Twin in Building Permit Processes

In many jurisdictions, building permits require that proposed developments comply with **natural hazard zoning**, including floodplains, wildfire risk areas, landslide zones, and seismic hazard zones. Traditionally, this

validation relies on consulting various sectoral datasets, which is time-consuming, error-prone, and often inconsistent.

This use case demonstrates how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automate the spatial intersection between a proposed building and official risk maps, while also verifying whether the design includes the required **adaptive measures** based on the identified risk.

Operational Scenario

During the building permit application, the applicant uploads a **georeferenced BIM model**. The DT platform then:

- Locates the project in relation to **official natural hazard maps** (e.g., floods, fires, seismic zones, unstable terrain).
- Detects whether the building intersects or is within a defined hazard zone (e.g., flood corridor, wildland-urban interface).
- Retrieves applicable regulatory measures (e.g., minimum elevation for habitable floors, fire-resistant materials, evacuation routes).
- Compares the design against these requirements and generates a **compliance report** with visual maps and references to the applicable regulation.

System Architecture

- A **georeferenced BIM model**, structured with levels, uses, materials, and space types (IfcBuilding, IfcSpace, IfcMaterial).
- **Authoritative GIS hazard layers**, provided by public agencies (e.g., Copernicus EMS, national flood databases, wildfire risk maps).
- A **regulatory rule catalog**, specifying adaptive design requirements per hazard zone, encoded in SHACL, RDF, or JSON-LD.
- A **multi-hazard spatial analysis engine**, evaluating location-based risk exposure and corresponding design responses.
- An **interactive hazard viewer**, overlaying risk zones with building geometry and compliance status.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Flood risk**: checks for minimum elevation of ground floors, absence of basements, and location outside high-flow zones.
- **Wildfire risk**: verifies defensible space setbacks and use of fire-resistant materials near forested areas.
- **Seismic zones**: ensures compatibility of geometry and structural systems with seismic codes.
- **Landslide/instable terrain**: avoids deep excavations or heavy underground elements in high-risk areas.
- **Emergency egress**: validates safe access and evacuation routes in high-risk contexts.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- Georeferenced BIM with precise spatial geometry and technical attributes.
- Access to official, up-to-date hazard layers in standard GIS formats (WFS, GeoTIFF, GeoJSON).
- Digitized regulatory conditions for adaptive measures per risk type.
- A DT platform with spatial validation capabilities and regulatory traceability.

Benefits

- **Avoids design approvals in high-risk zones without appropriate mitigation.**
- **Reduces legal liability for public authorities** by relying on authoritative data and automated traceability.
- **Allows for early adaptation of building design** to hazard exposure, reducing future risk and cost.
- **Facilitates reporting to external agencies**, such as environmental or civil protection authorities.
- **Supports urban resilience and alignment with EU directives**, such as the Floods Directive or climate adaptation policies.

Use Case 13: Automated Validation of Public Facility Allocations and Land Use Balance in Urban Developments Using a Digital Twin

In large-scale urban developments and subdivision projects, urban planning regulations often require that a defined portion of land or buildable area be allocated to **public or collective facilities** (e.g., green spaces, schools, health centers, civic buildings, public parking). Furthermore, a **balanced distribution of land uses** must be ensured between private and public functions.

This verification process—especially when involving multiple plots, development phases, or stakeholders—is complex and hard to manage manually. A **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automate this assessment at the level of urban development projects or planning instruments.

Operational Scenario

During the building permit application (or urbanization project phase), the developer submits a set of **BIM models and/or parcel division plans**.

The DT platform:

- Geolocates the parcels and extracts spatial surfaces and intended uses from the model (IfcSite, IfcZone, IfcBuilding + Psets).
- Loads the applicable **urban planning regulations** (zoning sheets, development plans, land use codes).
- Automatically calculates:
 - Total developable area.
 - Surface areas by use category: residential, commercial, public facilities, green space, roads.
 - Percentage allocated to each use.
- Compares the actual land-use distribution with **statutory requirements** (e.g., 15% public facilities, 20% green areas, 1 school seat per 100 dwellings).
- Generates a compliance or non-compliance report with a breakdown per phase, use, or developer.

System Architecture

- **BIM and/or GIS models** with semantically structured spatial entities by use category.
- **Structured regulatory rules** defining minimum land use quotas and functional ratios (e.g., square meters per resident).
- **Computational engine** for area aggregation and normative evaluation by zone and phase.
- **Multilayer compliance viewer**, displaying use allocations, zoning overlays, and regulatory thresholds.
- **Automated technical report**, exportable to urban planning dossiers and permitting workflows.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Minimum allocation of land for public facilities** (e.g., schools, health, parks).
- **Use balance validation** across the development area, including private and public categories.
- **Net and gross surface calculations** by land use.
- **Functional ratios**, such as parking spaces, school seats, or open space per household.
- **Progressive compliance checks** for phased urbanization or multi-party developments.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- Well-structured BIM or GIS models, classified by use type and surface.
- Digitized urban plans and normative datasets, structured for computation.
- DT platform capable of territorial, semantic, and percentage-based analysis.

Benefits

- **Ensures regulatory compliance in complex, multi-phase urban developments.**
- **Facilitates early validation of planning scenarios**, before formal commitments.
- **Supports coordination across stakeholders**, such as public authorities and private developers.
- **Promotes equitable urban development** with access to public services and green space.
- **Reduces time and conflict in the urban planning and permitting processes.**

Use Case 14: Automated Validation of Consistency Between Executed Model and Approved Building Permit Using a Digital Twin

After a building permit has been granted, urban control procedures must ensure that **the constructed building matches the approved project**. However, on-site modifications are common and can lead to deviations in aspects such as height, footprint, floor area, use, or materials.

This use case describes how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform** can automate the comparison between the **as-designed model (approved)** and the **as-built model (executed)**, enabling detection of inconsistencies and formal documentation of justified changes.

Operational Scenario

During the construction phase or upon project completion, the contractor or project owner provides an **as-built IFC model**, based on 3D scans, construction monitoring, or technical supervision.

The DT platform:

- Loads both the **approved (as-designed)** and **executed (as-built)** IFC models.
- Performs a comparative analysis at geometric, semantic, and regulatory levels:
 - Differences in height, volume, total floor area.
 - Changes in assigned functional use (e.g., from storage to residential).
 - Modifications in regulated elements (e.g., windows, access points, setbacks).
- Generates a structured discrepancy report, classifying changes as:
 - **Minor** (no legal relevance),
 - **Tolerable** (require technical justification),
 - **Substantial** (may require permit amendment).

System Architecture

- IFC model of the approved project (**as-designed**) and post-construction model (**as-built**) with consistent structure and naming.
- **BIM-to-BIM comparison engine**, applying geometric and semantic tolerance rules.
- **Catalog of legally significant elements**, weighted by regulatory impact (e.g., height = high, façade color = low).
- **3D difference viewer**, color-coded by type and severity of discrepancy.
- **Automated report generator**, linking to regulatory articles and possible administrative actions.

Types of Supported Validation

- **Volumetric comparison** (building width, height, depth).
- **Authorized vs. constructed floor area**.
- **Interior space distribution and functional use changes**.
- **Critical regulated components**: accessibility, fire evacuation paths, building alignment, boundary setbacks.
- **Detection of unauthorized works or unapproved additions**.

Requirements and Benefits

Requirements

- Updated and normalized IFC models with aligned naming and classification.
- Structured regulations identifying sensitive building elements.
- DT platform capable of high-precision comparison and legal traceability.

Benefits

- **Facilitates legal compliance monitoring during and after construction.**
- **Reduces the need for subjective on-site inspections.**
- **Enables generation of digital conformity certificates.**
- **Helps anticipate the need for permit amendments or regularization.**
- **Improves transparency between public authorities, developers, and contractors.**

Use Case 15: Real Estate Valuation Supported by Digital Twins through Integrated BIM-GIS and Spatial Analytics

Real estate appraisal is a fundamental process for taxation, financial planning, market analysis, and investment decision-making. Traditional valuation methods, often based on manual inspection, limited documentation, and non-standardized criteria, frequently suffer from issues related to subjectivity, lack of traceability, and limited scalability.

This use case outlines how a **Digital Twin (DT) platform**, integrating Building Information Models (BIM), geospatial data, and market intelligence, can be used to generate **accurate, objective, and reproducible property valuations** by leveraging technical attributes, spatial context, and regulatory constraints.

Operational Scenario

An appraiser—either from a public administration or a certified valuation firm—accesses the municipality’s DT platform, which hosts an IFC 4.3-compliant model of the building, fully georeferenced and enriched with descriptive metadata and contextual information.

The platform performs an automated assessment of critical building attributes, such as:

- Gross and usable floor areas, per story and per usage type
- Functional typology of spaces (residential units, circulation, service areas)
- Structural materials and construction quality
- Accessibility, orientation, daylight availability, and ventilation
- Normative compliance (e.g., habitability, energy efficiency, fire safety)

In parallel, GIS datasets are overlaid to assess the building’s surroundings, including:

- Official land value by cadastral block or planning zone
- Proximity to urban services, public transport, and green areas
- Environmental quality indicators (e.g., air quality, noise exposure)
- Local property transaction histories and price trends
- Zoning constraints affecting buildable potential or allowed uses

Based on this information, the system computes a set of valuation indicators, such as market-adjusted unit value, replacement cost, location-based adjustment coefficients, and depreciation ratios. These values may be exported into certified appraisal reports, decision-support dashboards, or integrated tax systems.

System Architecture

The valuation system comprises the following technical components:

- A **BIM repository** storing structured IFC 4.3 models with valuation-relevant property sets (e.g., finishes, condition, certifications)
- A **geospatial analytics engine** connected to authoritative GIS layers (cadastral maps, zoning, infrastructure, environmental datasets)
- A **real estate market database**, providing comparable sales data, assessed values, and temporal trends
- A **valuation computation engine**, applying national or international formulas (e.g., Spanish ECO/805/2003, RICS Red Book), adjusted using technical and spatial factors
- A **results interface**, offering traceable visualization of valuation components, data sources, and adjustment criteria

Types of Indicators Computed

The platform supports the calculation of various valuation outputs, including:

- **Replacement cost** based on surface area, typology, and construction quality
- **Location-adjusted value**, reflecting proximity to amenities, transport, and environmental quality
- **Estimated fiscal value**, in line with cadastral norms or tax regulations
- **Spatial efficiency index**, measuring usable area ratios
- **Projected market value**, derived from real-time comparables and automated correction factors

Implementation Requirements and Benefits

To operate effectively, the system requires:

- Detailed, semantically enriched IFC models
- Normalized GIS datasets compliant with INSPIRE or OGC standards
- Access to property market data or transaction registries

The primary benefits include:

- **Improved precision and reproducibility** in valuation processes
- **Standardization of valuation criteria** across assessors and jurisdictions
- **Full transparency and traceability** of valuation factors
- **Capacity for batch or scenario-based appraisals**
- **Alignment with digital tax systems and smart city financial strategies**

Integrating GIS into building permitting processes offers significant benefits, enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and transparency. By utilizing GIS technology, permit inspectors can analyze spatial data with precision, ensuring that all building plans comply with relevant regulations and standards. This integration not only reduces the time required for processing permits by providing immediate access to critical geographic information but also supports comprehensive decision-making. Additionally, GIS facilitates better communication and collaboration among stakeholders by offering a visual representation of spatial data, which aids in consensus building and increases public participation. Ultimately, the adoption of GIS in building permitting leads to improved regulatory compliance, optimized workflows, and a more transparent and engaging process for all involved. Among the benefits are:

Long-term Goals of the Space Hierarchy Service:

- **Increase Efficiency:** Enhance the efficiency of municipal operations.
- **Shorter Processing Time:** Reduce the time required for processing tasks.
- **Support the Comprehensiveness of Work:** Aid in the thoroughness and completeness of work processes.
- **Improvement of Participation:** Boost engagement and participation from stakeholders.
- **Better Image of the Organization:** Improve the public perception and image of the municipality.

Short-term Goals of the Space Hierarchy Service:

- **Create Knowledge:** Generate and disseminate valuable knowledge.
- **Reach Consensus:** Facilitate consensus-building among stakeholders.
- **Human and Machine Readable:** Ensure information is accessible and readable by both humans and machines.
- **Process Improvement:** Drive improvements in processes and workflows.
- **Increase Job Satisfaction:** Enhance job satisfaction for employees.

Experiences in the use of digital twins

The Estonian scenario

Estonia, well-known for its leadership in digital technologies, has made digital twins a key part of its urban and construction infrastructure. In this context, a **digital twin is a virtual copy of physical entities that can include buildings, infrastructures, and even entire cities**. This advanced technology allows for simulations and analyses that can greatly improve urban planning and construction project management, making processes more efficient.

Figure 8.- Estonia Digital Twin

In Estonia, the "three 3D digital twins" are important digital projects. They help with city planning and land management. These are:

1. Tallinn 3D city model (Linnamudel)

- **Description:** This 3D model is managed by the city of Tallinn and uses the Esri ArcGIS platform.
- **Functions:** It shows a detailed digital model of Tallinn's buildings, streets, and other parts of the city.
- **Benefits:** It helps with city planning, infrastructure management, and decision-making. People can see and understand city projects better.

2. Estonian Land Board prototype 3D model

- **Description:** This 3D model is managed by the Estonian Land Board and also uses the Esri ArcGIS platform.
- **Functions:** It shows a 3D model of Estonia's land, including topography and land use. It is useful for planning and managing land and natural resources.
- **Benefits:** It helps with accurate land management and infrastructure planning. It also supports environmental conservation and emergency response.

3. E-construction platform 3D Digital Twin

- **Description:** Developed by the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, this platform uses mostly open-source tools like Cesium for 3D visualization.
- **Functions:** It integrates construction and planning data in a 3D environment, helping with design, construction, and management of buildings and infrastructure.

- **Benefits:** It speeds up construction processes, improves project accuracy, and reduces costs. It also encourages innovation in the construction sector with advanced digital technologies.

These three 3D digital twins show Estonia's commitment to **advanced digitalization and technology, providing modern tools for urban, land, and infrastructure management.**

The adoption of digital twins in Estonia shows its proactive approach and commitment to technological innovation in both public and private management. **These virtual models allow urban planners and project developers to see the impact of their ideas before they are implemented, which reduces costs and increases project sustainability.** Additionally, the ability to simulate different scenarios provides a valuable tool for strategic and operational decision-making, adapting to future changes and needs without compromising current resources.

The vision for digital twins in Estonia aims to **integrate and model urban, geographic, and environmental data into a unified platform.** This platform will enable detailed simulation and analysis of both urban and rural environments. This approach helps in understanding and managing the spaces better, ensuring efficient planning and sustainable development.

This integrated approach not only improves coordination across various sectors such as construction, traffic management, and public services but also fosters a collaborative environment between government agencies, businesses, and citizens. Thus, Estonia continues to strengthen its position as a **global leader in digital technology**, leading the way to more efficient and participatory urban management.

Challenges encountered

Several key challenges were identified in the development and implementation of the Estonian Urban Digital Twins. These challenges can be classified into different categories including data collection, data integration, visualisation and real-time updating. Here is a detailed description of each of these challenges:

1. Data collection

- **Quality and method of data collection:** Determining what data is needed to create a digital representation of the city is one of the first hurdles. This involves not only the content of the data, but also the ownership, format, protection and privacy of the data, as well as the complexity and level of abstraction of the data.

2. Data integration

- **Data heterogeneity:** Urban data are diverse in types and formats, making them difficult to analyse immediately in smart city systems. Effective integration of this heterogeneous data requires advanced methods to ensure the consistency and usefulness of the information.
- **Interoperability and standards:** Unified models, frameworks and structures are crucial for real-time data mergers, enabling seamless connections between physical and virtual data exchange. The lack of universally accepted terminology to describe real and virtual objects is a significant challenge.

3. Data visualization

- **Data display:** Presenting data in a way that is attractive and easy for users to understand is a challenge. This includes the user experience and appearance of digital models, as well as appropriate levels of realism and detail.
- **Realism:** Achieving the right level of realism is crucial to enhance the user experience. The challenge lies in creating experimental expressions that are consistent with the related real space.
- **Abstraction of complexity:** A visualisation that is too abstract or complex can affect users' understanding. In the early stages of a planning process, excessive detail and visual realism are often not needed.

4. Real-time updates

- **Regular and real-time updates:** Digital Twins need to be updated regularly and, if necessary, in real time. Managing updates, especially when integrating new datasets such as LiDAR, presents significant challenges.

5. Cybersecurity

- **Data security:** Cyber-attacks can have serious consequences, including the disclosure of sensitive information and taking control of critical infrastructure systems.

6. Accessibility and ownership

- **Clarity of ownership:** Uncertain ownership of data can lead to long-term access problems. In collaborative projects, debates about ownership and intellectual property rights may arise.
- **Accessibility:** There must be a balance between providing unrestricted access for citizens to test scenarios and avoiding the feeling of not influencing the planning process.

Each of these challenges requires specific and considered solutions, adapted to the particular urban and technological context of each city. This table provides a clear picture of how the City of Tallinn has addressed the practical challenges in implementing its digital urban twin model.

Challenge	Tallinn's Approach/Solution
Data Collection	Outsourced to external companies. Hiring a machine learning specialist.
Data Integration	Acquisition through clouds with predefined rules and storage in Azure hub.
Interoperability	Data must be provided only with corresponding standards by partners.
Linking	Two options: 1) Manual data download, 2) Connection through APIs.
Data Conversion	Data from different sources are converted and structured into a unified format. Sometimes done with additional software, e.g., FME.
Real-time Data	Currently tested in pilot projects, restricted access to city authorities.
Visualization	Web-based platform and in the city center (AvaLinn) through projection and the possibility of using shutter glasses (3D) as well as on screens.
Degree of Realism	Subjective decisions are made by the responsible 3D specialists.
Abstraction	The 3D specialists decide what to include or exclude.
Ownership	The city owns the data and uses Esri software for visualization in Linnamudel.
Accessibility	Modification is restricted; the challenge is how to activate business owners to use the Linnamudel.
Cybersecurity	Strict European and Estonian data security and privacy laws must be followed.
Implementation	For urban planning, citizen participation, and collaborative processes.
Platform	Web-based platform powered by ArcGIS (Esri).

The implementation of digital twins in Estonia represents a significant advancement in the way urban environments are planned, built, and managed. Although there are significant challenges with data integration, the benefits of this technology, such as improved efficiency in licensing processes and more informed and sustainable urban planning, are clear. Estonia continues to lead in adopting digital technologies that can serve as a model for other countries in the future.

Use of the Digital Twin in Planning and Construction

In the construction sector, digital twins in Estonia could be used to optimize the design and construction of buildings and other infrastructure. This would allow architects, engineers, and urban planners to better visualize projects and make adjustments before and during the physical construction.

In Estonia, the following data are integrated into the digital twins, which are listed below along with their source of origin and how they could be used for permit checks:

Data	Origin	Requirement
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Spatial planning requirements	Planning register	Building height, Buildable area on the parcel
Existing and planned buildings	Property register, Cadastre	Proximity to neighboring buildings, Availability of sunlight
Cadastral parcels	Cadastre	Distance to boundary
Public service networks	Property register, Construction register	Pipes or cables within the construction zone that must be preserved
Environmental restrictions	Environmental agency	Proximity to water bodies, Proximity to nature reserves
Flood risk zones	Environmental agency	Flood risk zones
Restrictions related to cultural heritage	Cultural heritage council	Conservation requirements for existing structures, Specific viewpoints
Roads	Road registry	Access requirements to the parcel from public roads
Air corridors	Aviation board	Building height restriction
Vegetation	Environmental agency	Trees and other green infrastructures